

Compilation of all data behind figures for Dryad/Zenodo

Fig. 1

Fig. 1a: No data

Fig. 1b: No data here. Crystal structure from .cif file provided directly to publisher

Fig. 1c: Broad absorption spectra and laser transmission

```
% Fig. 1c Broad absorption spectra
% x1c_1: energy eV
% y1c_1: UV-VIS absorption normalized to transition IV
% y2c_2: UV-VIS absorption normalized to ligand absorption
%clear;
load('fig1.mat');
plot(x1c_1, y1c_1);
xlim([1.15 1.5]); ylim([-0.05 1.05]);
```



```
plot(x1c_1, y1c_2);
xlim([0.8 3.5]); ylim([-0.05 1.05]);
```



```
% Fig. 1c Laser transmission spectrum  
% x1c_2: energy eV  
% y1c_3: laser transmission converted to absorption of IV  
plot(x1c_2,y1c_3);
```



```
% Fig. 1d Emission spectrum of transitions IV and V  
% x1d: energy eV  
% y1d: emission  
plot(x1d, y1d);  
xlim([1.15 1.4]);
```


Fig. 2

Fig. 2a & b: Temperature-dependent absorption data

Fig. 2c & d: No data

Fig. 2e: Spectral hole burning data

```

% Fig. 2a absorption data with varying temperatures
% liquid nitrogen data (black), liquid helium data (blue)
% x2a_{temp} frequency THz
% y2a_{temp} transmission mV
load('fig2.mat')
gap = 0.3;
plot(x2a_320,y2a_320+gap*21,'b'); hold on;
plot(x2a_310,y2a_310+gap*20,'b');
plot(x2a_300(:,1),y2a_300+gap*19,'b');
plot(x2a_148,(y2a_148-0.08)*0.5/1.45+gap*17,'k');
plot(x2a_138,(y2a_138-0.08)*0.5/1.45+gap*16,'k');
plot(x2a_128,(y2a_128-0.08)*0.5/1.45+gap*15,'k');
plot(x2a_118,(y2a_118-0.08)*0.5/1.45+gap*14,'k');
plot(x2a_108,(y2a_108-0.08)*0.5/1.45+gap*13,'k');
plot(x2a_98,(y2a_98-0.08)*0.5/1.45+gap*12,'k');
plot(x2a_95,y2a_95+gap*11,'b');
plot(x2a_88,(y2a_88-0.08)*0.5/1.45+gap*10,'k');
plot(x2a_85,y2a_85+gap*9,'b');
plot(x2a_78,(y2a_78-0.08)*0.5/1.45+gap*8,'k');
plot(x2a_75,y2a_75+gap*7,'b');
plot(x2a_65,y2a_65+gap*6,'b');

```

```

plot(x2a_55,y2a_55+gap*5,'b');
plot(x2a_45,y2a_45+gap*4,'b');
plot(x2a_35,y2a_35+gap*3,'b');
plot(x2a_25,y2a_25+gap*2,'b');
plot(x2a_15,y2a_15+gap,'b');
plot(x2a_7,y2a_7,'b');
plot(305.4822*[1 1],7*[-1 1],'k');
plot(305.5527*[1 1],7*[-1 1],'k');
hold off;
xlim([305 306]);
ylim([-0.3 7]);
legend('320K','310K','300K','148K','138K','128K','118K','108K','98K','95K',...
      '88K','85K','78K','75K','65K','55K','45K','35K','25K','15K','7K','location','eastor

```



```

% Fig. 2e spectral hole burning data
% x2e: frequency kHz
% y2e: probe transmission mV
plot(x2e, y2e);

```


Fig. 3

Fig. 3a: absorption data of various Yb transitions from literature are traced from the papers and data of our samples are experimentally obtained. The absorption data for (thiolfan)YbCl(THF) is provided in fig. 1c and the data for (thiolfan*)YbCl(THF)₂ is provided here.

Fig. 3b: same data as 3a.

```
% Fig. 3a
% (2), (thiolfan*)YbCl(THF)2
% x3a_1: energy eV
% y3a_1: absorption
load('fig3.mat')
plot(x3a_1, y3a_1);
```



```
% (3)  
% x3a_2: wavelength nm  
% y3a_2: traced absorption of (3), ref. 26  
plot(x3a_2,y3a_2);
```



```
% (4)  
% x3a_3: energy eV  
% y3a_3: traced absorption of (4), ref. 27  
plot(x3a_3, y3a_3);
```



```
% (5)  
% x3a_4: energy eV  
% y3a_4: traced absorption of (5), ref. 28  
plot(x3a_4, y3a_4);
```



```
% (6)  
% x3a_5: energy eV  
% y3a_5: traced absorption of (6), ref. 29  
plot(x3a_5,y3a_5);
```


Fig. 4

Fig. 4a & b: No data

Fig. 4c: Absorption and emission data provided in fig. 1c and 1d. Oscillator strengths provided in Table S8.

Fig. 5

Fig. 5a: absorption with sigma +/- light

Fig. 5b: magnetic circular dichroism signal at varying B strengths

Fig. 5c: images from movie S1

Fig. 5d: MCD with DC field

Fig. 5e & f: MCD signal over time with varying AC field strength

```

% Fig. 5a absorption with sigma +/- light
load('fig5.mat')
% x5a_1 frequency THz
% x5a_2 frequency THz
% y5a_1 sigma - absorption
% y5a_2 sigma + absorption
plot(x5a_1, y5a_1); hold on;
plot(x5a_2, y5a_2); hold off;

```



```
% Fig. 5b MCD at varying B strengths  
% x5b_1 energy eV  
% x5b_2 energy eV  
% x5b_3 energy eV  
% y5b_1 differential absorption under 0T  
% y5b_2 differential absorption under 0.16T  
% y5b_3 differential absorption under 0.38T  
plot(x5b_1, y5b_1); hold on;  
plot(x5b_2, y5b_2);  
plot(x5b_3, y5b_3); hold off;
```



```
% Fig. 5d MCD with varying DC fields  
% x5d B field (T)  
% y5d spectrum analyzer amplitude in V  
plot(x5d, y5d, 'o');
```



```
% Fig. 5e MCD signal over time with varying AC fields
% x5f_1 time (s)
% y5f_1 spectrum analyzer amplitude (dBm) of sample
% x5f_2 time (s)
% y5f_2 spectrum analyzer amplitude (dBm) of air
% x5f_3 time (s)
% y5f_3 spectrum analyzer amplitude (dBm) of THF solvent
plot(x5f_1, y5f_1, 'o'); hold on;
plot(x5f_2, y5f_2, 'o');
plot(x5f_3, y5f_3, 'o'); hold off;
```

